
The role of Taiwan state in developing small local communities - The Cases of traditional crafts in Red house market in Taipei and the traditional clothing store, in Taoyuan

Mohd. Ali Khawaldeh
Doctoral Student
Social Sciences Department
National Chengchi University

Abstract

The role of state institutions in Taiwan highlights in the management and organization of work in small communities, although this is not consistent with modern management theories, which calls for a focus on showing the roles of the local community by encouraging them to participate more effectively, with a view across the spectrum of community development, generally and specifically small communities. Hence, this requires the identification of the reasons for this practice, and to clarify the implications of this method on each of the small communities and the state. This article addresses the traditional crafts community, which is considered one of the most important sources of study of the history and culture of the countries. In addition to shedding light on Taiwan's experience in this field through study of real-life situations, as in the case of collective traditional craft market, that is a red house market, in Taipei, as well as an individual case, that is the traditional clothing store, in Taoyuan. The third and last part of study is conclusion

Key words: local community, small community, traditional craft markets.

1. INTRODUCTION

The state's role in managing and intervention in the communities contrasts with changing time. It can be widened and narrowed from time to time depending on the progress and development of communities necessary to achieve overall objectives of these communities (1). Previous era of the last century characterized with greater role of the state, and its

interference in pettiness and accurate things in the life of society. The globalization phenomenon and administrative systems have opened new horizons for the state to give up its role in the direct management of local communities, especially at the lower levels, such as small communities (2).

The limited role of the state is to encourage members of civil society in small communities to interact with the state institutions in a positive way and strengthen the affiliation to it (3).

The state which owns the successful management is not that just take it upon themselves to find food, clothing and housing to individuals, but to consider every citizen as wealth nationalism and the availability has the right climate to invest his energies and talents to the service of his country (4). It is to exceed this outburst of tender energies, creativity existing in its citizens. The past experience has shown that the institutions of civil society seriously weakened because of the problems and constraints that faced them. Some scientists believe that the advantage of the globalization system is only achieved when the state is able to develop institutions to achieve a sound and equitable development (5).

Everyone knows the status of government administration in Taiwan is advanced and sophisticated, so it is considered as model by other countries. Also it's taken as reference in the development of modern government administrative concepts. Therefore, it is necessary to search for appropriate clarifications and reasons for the intervention of Taiwanese state in regulating various

traditional craft markets by study one collective case and another individual case.

This paper consists of several parts: the first part is the theoretical framework includes a study of the major theoretical essays, opinions of scientists and researchers in the field of administration and government performance, various information and scientific studies. The second part, which represents the practical framework through study of real-life situations, as in the case of collective traditional craft market, that is a red house market, in Taipei, as well as an individual case, the study is the traditional apparel store, in Taoyuan. The third and last part is the conclusions of the study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

What is the state's role in developing small communities? Diverse opinions and views of the group highlights the difference in the reasons for state intervention any role in the development of societies in various shades and levels, either big ones or small. Since this theory is contrary to the most fundamental principles of modern management. In this context, many researchers opposed to this trend of theory. Dennis, et al (6) assert that this represents a challenge for political and administrative leaders in all countries is to redefine the roles of government and to build the capacity of public and private institutions to play beneficial roles in helping citizens to cope with the uncertainties, and benefit from the opportunities of globalization. David Osborne and Ted Gaebler (7) summarized the principles and characteristics of the New Public Management movement. They described ten characteristics of what effective governments should be; the most important is the Community-empowering in ways that encourage local groups to solve their own problems rather than dictating bureaucratic solutions.

Moussaoui Riad (2008/2009) defines the concept of development that is to provide a productive work and the quality of life better for all people and it is what needs to be significant growth in productivity and income and the development of human ability, and according to this vision, the goal of development is not just to increase production, but enabling people to expand their options and so the development process is the process of becoming a capacity development and the process is not only to maximize the benefit or economic well-being, but the rise level of cultural, social and economic.

This debate shows that the point of view of scientists and researchers about the role of the state in developing small communities, contrary to the theory of the article. This leads us to adopt scientific method in analyzing some basic concepts to prove or deny

the theory. The article can cover this by studying: good state specifications, elements of small communities, and the state's role in the management of traditional crafts markets.

2.1 Good state specifications

The role of the state to manage communities is a variable subject, where evolve as affected by what is going on around it of events and new concepts. In the past, it influenced by the concepts of intellectual and ideological orientations, currently it has been affected in two concepts: first, globalization and its impact on what governments must adapt and respond to the rapid change in the international economic (8), social, political and technological trends. Globalization has brought both benefits and challenges to countries around the world (9). Second, increasing discontent among citizens in many countries of government functions and services provided by public administrations. The government should always seek ways to "do more with less expense." This can be achieved through the following: the application of new technologies to make government functions more efficient, and the fight against corruption through education, prevention and sanctions, the professionalization of the public service through career development and training programs (10); and the lifting of restrictions so that the government does not hinder its citizens to participate effectively in the global economy, and broaden their horizons

Taiwan is state of the leading developed countries in applying the concepts of modern administration science. It is always seeking to boost developing state communities at various levels. Moreover, it is one of the most important references in government administration field for some other countries. It is no secret that the importance of adopting the direct supervision over managing markets in traditional craft. Due to privacy and importance of this sector at the national level that is clear for everyone.

2.2 Importance of The traditional crafts

The traditional crafts and culture are two sides of the same coin, each of them is important from a historical perspective, the two complement each other. No one can deny the role of either of them (11). Cultural richness of its value, but it needs a professional broker who is able to prescribe in all of mastering and accuracy to give its real features and attributes, and let the peoples get the right benefit of it. Culture is the values, customs, traditions, knowledge, arts, and different patterns of social life living social framework (12). It represents the identity and heritage (13), which is continuity between peoples passed on through generations of

experience, science, and knowledge. As well as encourages creativity, innovation, and modernization, in line with the requirements of society and its needs, to enrich moral concepts are which are affecting the people such as patience, determination, perseverance, and good treatment.

No matter how big a cultural component to be successful but also need transfer means which is capable to convey achievements among the nations through different stages of history, especially in light of the scarcity of technological capabilities in the old ancient times. The inimitable talents for the owners of skilled hands excelled in filming and transfer of all the different kinds of culture between the generations to the present day. The owners of these skills and creations deserve the attention (14). Feeling that these states institutions with interest over economic development, which is invaluable and urging them to tender more than a factor of stability for them, and rare professions, this supports the others to continue the effort and diligence

Institutional and administrative system is one of the most important factors that need to be addressed to provide better services for rare professions, in terms of the mechanism of service delivery and development, and how to employ most important government capacity to support the most important components of society, cultural and humanitarian. As a result of the advanced level, which is characterized by a Taiwan from other countries in the preservation of traditional values, it is based on the legacy of institutional management which adopts the applied approach, not only theoretical. How Taiwan has been able to create the conditions, and create opportunities for a high-end creative art, creative skills in accuracy caused to the viewer fascination and admiration.

The visiting tourist sites or tourist gatherings marvel at the amount of good organization and preparation of public spaces in Taiwan. This in itself reflects the amount professionalism, excellence, good management, and strict regulation planned properly. It is noted that a good choice highlights in many ways in terms of location, capacity, attached, Avatar costs in services to users, diversity of offerings, achieve maximum benefits for the biggest slice of the local community

The activities of public tourist places that used in Taiwan are realistic examples of institutional management disciplined, accurate planning and preparation. The Red House (15) is an example of the typical market for all markets, which distributed across the country. The market design commensurate with the available resources, a high level of discipline and management, reflecting the bright image of the products and crafts available in the market, it shows

amount of institutional development of Taiwan government, it generates the desire for visits from the link place, and it attracts the tourist to enjoy the shopping and touring (16). This market can record excellence and uniqueness of Taiwan from other countries, in institutional development administrative in the tourist industry, which the other countries cannot keep up with Taiwan. Article looking for the causes of currently the Red House market Excellence, and the ways of developing the market for the better.

2.3 Project Objectives

The establishment of the market aims to achieve a number of objectives at once. These objectives are as follows: First. Developing cross-section of the local community in traditional crafts distinct rare, so that keeps the cultural heritage across different times (17), and reflects the noble human values. Second, providing a sound infrastructure that could talents appear and provide them with a secure life ", the function is stable, that this is not generated only by maximizing collective work, which fosters a sense of possibility to take advantage of available common traits by the owners of this character, it appears through study case the traditional apparel store in the town of Bade in the city to update, which shows that the presence of an individual case does not generate a firm desire and does not translate to spur the tourist to visit this place, and this is a foil to the owner of this store, because he did not achieve physical yield sufficient, Third, the confirmation that the message is symbolic, and not to target profitability. This highlights clearly through the provision of a variety of government services to the owners of the shops, at discounted prices, for example, the depreciation of rent shops compared with the value of rent in nearby shops. Fourth, activate tourism movement across the country by attracting foreign tourists to different themes and distinctive sites. Fifth, activate the economic movement in the country in general, and the region surrounding the commercial market in particular. Sixth, shedding light on the institutional administrative capacity of Taiwan's governments planning in the long-term (18), this has emerged since the founding of the market in 1907.

2.4 Elements Power in establishing the traditional red house market

Elements power of institutional management of Taiwan's government stand out through good planning and implementation. Emphasis has been placed on reasons that contribute to success, and overcome the difficulties and obstacles. It focused attention on the following key points:

2.5 Importance of Location

The place must be characterized with specifications meeting all the necessary requirements to provide better service for workers and visitors alike. The most important distinction in traditional red house market site, the following: first point, the historical significance given the importance of the Red House building in terms of design and architecture, it dazzles the visitor in terms of the art of the ancient architecture, inspired by the past. The Red House, a Western-style red-brick octagonal structure in Taipei's Ximen space built in 1908 (19), is Taiwan's first public market and the most well preserved class III historical site. It was designed by Kondo Juro, a western-styled architect in the prefectural civil engineering office at the time. Second point, In November, 2007, Department of Cultural Affairs commissioned Taipei Culture Foundation to manage The Red House. It underwent a series of cultural transformation including: Octagon Building 2F Theater, Central Display Area, Grid of Hundred Treasures, Cho West Cha, The Red House Boutique Area, at Cruciform Building Creative Boutique, Cultural Arts Exhibition Platform, Riverside Live House, Market for Artists & Designers located and Moonlight Movie Theater by North Square and Outdoor Café located by South Square. The place is close to the administrative services, where there are many restaurants and cafes of various levels, reasonable prices, and tastes. These changes provided better services to the general public, created a space of creativity, attracted crowds, and expanded the domain of overlapping cultural arts. The Red House has successfully transformed into a new cultural & creative industries development center in Taipei City. Third point. Easy access to it, as it is located close to the means of communication and transport, for example, Ximen train station is only a hundred meters away from the site, this allows the visitor to coordinate visit several tourist sites in the same day and within a short period.

2.6 Diversity

Farsighted planning which represents the administrative style of the founders, the goal to broaden participation to include several axes: First, the diversity of the local arts participation in the market mismatch regular glass artifacts, and the cycle of the air, shapes of wood, clothing lacy, watch archaeological, paintings, metal-cutting colorful, decorative pieces and ornaments, traditional arts and other light (20). Second, which included make way for various arts, spectrum, and civilizations, where the organizers allowed the participation of some

traditional craftsmen of other nation, such as the art of the Jordanian colored sand, which is a burden inside the bottles, this art represents a rare era of thousands of years, since the era of Neapten civilization that lived in the ancient city of Petra (21). Third, that is singled out to take advantage of the proximity of some outstanding individual performances, presented in open spaces nearby, such as acrobatic performances, concerts, as well as other artistic performances. All these themes have supported the market take advantage of the various programs of tourism visits.

2.7 Organization

The market regulation is one of the most attractive points of visitor's attention. The organizers divided the market into two main parts: the fixed department stores, which are located inside building called Red House, which is open seven days a week, this type of stores newly opened. The other type is temporary stores, located outside the building in small makeshift tents, which opens only during the weekend from two o'clock until ten o'clock in the evening.

In this organization have been involved in mind that the conditions for those who wish to be limited only by the end of the week, or permanently throughout the week. The multiplicity of exits or entrances to the market and diversity, enhance access to the market from various quarters easily, and quickly, especially in times of crisis suffocating traffic. Good market regulation protrudes through the unification of the colors of the tents used in white that provides by the organizers. Nutshell, this gives the harmonious appearance of the market, and prevent chaos and moods. The determination of the working hours, make it easier for employees and visitors to organize their appointments commensurate with these times.

2.8 Development

Development process must be continued, and that does not stop at a certain limit. The importance of traditional crafts is given in highlighting Taiwan's cultural manifestations. The Government of Taiwan could have direct control of the development process, for several reasons: first. It continues to provide top service throughout the week instead of being limited to the weekend just so some citizens were permitted to work throughout the week through rental stores in the Red house building. Second, the provision of basic requirements for the market through market Department under the supervision of the Government to ensure consistency and uniformity in the infrastructure market, where all the stores are equipped with white tents, chairs and tables are the standard colors which increased the aesthetics of the

site. Third, supervisory leadership, given that most traditional craftsmen are busy with other work and working part-time, are dedicated to work, the level of planning for development requires high qualification level of who can do the work of administrative leadership (22). All the above reasons it pays to the leadership of the Government intervention in the market through an official representative, and those points that allow the State to direct supervision on these projects. Also, there may be a future perspective for the development of the market by increasing the flow of tourist groups and provide tourist offices with appropriate times to visit the market

3. DISCUSSION

We observe through review previous topics, some important points have emerged had to reflect for the following reasons: first, the importance of global competitiveness requires that administrative level evolved matches the competition with States and other Nations under the era of globalization and evolving technology. Second, the importance of craftsmanship being reflected the cultural level of the State. Third, lack of qualification management for the owners of this craft as a result of part-time work in addition to academic level is likely less than the level of strategic planning. Fourth, that State support is better than limited potential owners of traditional craft appeared through the place, infrastructure management, consistency, and diversification. Fifth, the level of collective action offers opportunities for greater success than individual initiative.

4. CONCLUSION

We conclude by saying, in the words of concise administrative theory, due to the meager economic resources of artisans who find it difficult to sustain his trade, government spending cannot be dispensed, as it functions as a shield to protect and nurture these infant industries. Moreover, Government spending allows weathering unforeseen economic exigencies, which at times these communities will not be prepared to face. The Red House has successfully transformed into a new cultural & creative industries development center in Taipei City. In 2008, it was awarded The 7th Urban Landscape Award in Historical Space Redevelopment. For the future studies, we hope to cover another part of community development.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Adnan al-Atiya Ramadan, an article, the Arab Revolt introductions and prospects, *Andalus Magazine*, 15/04/1432.
- [2]. Nayyar, Deepak (edited), 2002. *Governing Globalization. Issues and Institutions*. Oxford University Press.
- [3]. Mohmed Abdul Wahab Al-Otaibi, civil society organizations origination mechanisms and tools to work and achieve the goals, the training program entitled (qualifying leaders and NGOs on democratic governance and the skills of the alliance and change), the Republic of Yemen, Taiz, the Women's Forum for Research and Training, May 4 to May 12, 2009, pp: 17-19.
- [4]. Eigen, Peter, "The Central Role of Civil Society in combating Corruption in the Era of Globalization", paper presented at transparency for growth conferences, Atlanta, Georgia, 1999.
- [5]. Cable, Vincent. "What future for the state," in *Dealalus*, March 22, 1995.
- [6]. G. Shabbir Cheema and Dennis A. Rondinelli, "Reinventing Government for the Twenty-First Century: State Capacity in a Globalizing Society", 1st (First) Edition, (2003).
- [7]. David Osborne and Ted Gaebler (1992), *Reinventing Government: How entrepreneurial spirit Is Transforming the Public Sector*.
- [8]. Stanley Hoffman, "Clash of Globalizations," *Foreign Affairs*, Vol. 81, No. 4 (2002): 104-115.
- [9]. Dennis A. Rondinelli and Jack N. Behrman, "The Promises and Pains of Globalization," *Global Focus - International Journal of Business, Politics and Social Policy*, Vol. 12, No. 1 (2000): 3-16.
- [10]. President Vicente Fox, "Foreword," in Dennis A. Rondinelli and G. Shabbir Cheema (eds.), *Reinventing Government for the Twenty-first Century: State Capacity in a Globalizing Society*. Stanford, CT: Kumarian Press (2003).
- [11]. Omar Amin son of Abdullah, the interaction of traditional crafts, tourism and cultural heritage and economic level, available at <https://historicalcities.wordpress.com/2009/02/07>
- [12]. Chen, W.C., January 2005. Development of Art of Metalsmithing in Colleges and

- Universities in Taiwan from 1985. Master's thesis, Graduate Institute of Visual Arts, National Pingtung University of Education.
- [13]. Ken Browne, Sociology for AS AQA, Polity Press 2008, 3d edition, pp:31-31.
- [14]. Shen, L.C., 2002. Analysis of Effect of Award Policy: Using Crafts Design Competition in Taiwan as an Example. Master's thesis, Executive Master of Public Affairs, Tunghai University.
- [15]. redhouse@redhouse.org.tw.
- [16]. Robert B. Denhardt, Janet Vinzant Denhart, Maria P. Aristigueta, Managing Human Behavior in Public & Nonprofit Organizations, Thousand Oaks, NEW Delhi, London, 2002, PP:195-198.
- [17]. Erich Avrami, Randall Mason, Marta de la Torre, Values and heritage conservation, Research Report, the Getty conservation institute, Los Angeles, Ca (2000), PP: 5-6.
- [18]. Edquist, C., Hommen, L. (eds), "Small Country Innovation Systems: Globalization, change, and policy in Asia and Europe", Cheltenham, Edward Elgar, PP: 31-70.
- [19]. Micki & Kristen, Ximen, Red House, available at 5/01/2010 07:30:00 AM, <http://wandering-taiwan.blogspot.tw/2010/05/ximen-red-house.html>, access at 20/05/2016.
- [20]. TSO LON-DI, Taipei's Old, but Hot, Red House, article, Taiwan Today, Sept. 1, 2009, access at May 20, 2016, <http://www.taiwantoday.tw/fp.asp?xItem=59956&CtNode=2181>.
- [21]. Sand Bottles, AlHakaya, article, available at May 20, 2016, http://www.alhakaya.net/category.php?id_category=58.
- [22]. Robert Durant, "Whither the Neoadministrative state? Toward a Polity-Centered Theory of administrative reform, Journal of public administration Researched Theory 10, no 1 (2000), PP: 79-109.

